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Agricultural Personnel and Job Satisfaction: A Case Study of Block Extension Agents in Ondo and Ekiti States of Nigeria

⁽¹⁾Wole-Alo F.I. ⁽²⁾Fasina O. O.

Department of Agricultural Extension and Communication Technology, Federal University of Technology, Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria.

Correspondence e-mail address: fiwolealo@futa.edu.ng/fellymee@yahoo.com

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Abstract

The study assessed job satisfaction among female agricultural extension agents in Ondo and Ekiti States. The study described the socio-economic characteristics of the female agricultural extension workers and their level of job satisfaction, their attitudes towards their job and the perceived factors influencing their job satisfaction. A total number of thirty-five respondents were interviewed and information was collected with the aid of well-structured questionnaire while data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics and regression. The result revealed that majority of the female agricultural extension workers slightly agree to their level of job satisfaction with the grand mean score of 3.63. The result also showed that majority of the female agricultural extension workers strongly agree with the attitude towards their job with the grand mean of 3.44. The result also revealed that regular payment of allowances, level of education, official status and promotion determine to a reasonable extent the level of job satisfaction and showed that majority of female extension workers often perform their role and responsibility.

Keywords: Job, satisfaction, female, Ondo and Ekiti states

1.0 Introduction

The impact of female agricultural extension agents in agriculture cannot be underestimated, but despite this just about 15% of the world's extension agents are women (GFRAS 2012). Recent studies have shown that women farmers who are supervised by female agricultural extension agents have more access to extension services than women farmers who work with male agricultural extension agents. Also studies have shown that extension agencies, staffed primarily by men, give preference to male farmers, sometimes even when women are wealthy and innovative managers of large farms (Staudt, 2006). As a result, many have called for the use of female agricultural extension agents as the primary means of aiding women farmers. Female agricultural extension agents may be more likely than men agents to establish contact with women farmers.

The importance of agricultural extension in the development of agriculture in Nigeria cannot be overemphasized as it is regarded as one of the educational inputs designed for farmers to help themselves. These programs helped to expand or extend the work of universities beyond the campus and neighbouring community (Ayangei, 2009). Agricultural extension activities in Nigeria have developed from the largely regulatory body of the Government rural administration with its main function of ensuring the adoption of improved technologies. At the time of independence the major government agency charged with agricultural extension and rural development functions were the ministry of agriculture which continues, to reflect this major involvement in rural development. However in Nigeria today, Agricultural Development Programs (ADP) plays the role of extension and delivery services in the agricultural sector (Ogunsunmi and Abegunde 2001).

The main and first feature of the ADP was its reliance on the small scale farmers as the central focus for

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increased food production. The projects were to be funded under a tripartite agreement involving World Bank 66%, Federal government 20% and State government 14% in addition to payments of salaries of local staff. The two main objectives of the ADPs were to increase food production, and to raise the income of small-scale farmers. Agricultural extension activities can only be carried out through the agricultural extension agents, therefore we need to have an idea of who is an extension agent and what is his/her role. An agricultural extension agent also known as the change agent is someone whose primary role is to achieve a transformation of attitudes behavior and social organization. (Matami, 2006). They are intermediaries between research and farmers. They operate as facilitators and communicators, helping farmers in their decision making and ensuring that appropriate knowledge is implemented to obtain the best results. They need to communicate to farmers on necessary information that can be useful to them. They also need to ensure that farmers understand this information and use it on their farms in order to obtain the best production. For agricultural extension agents to be effective, they need to be motivated and satisfied with their occupation.

Job satisfaction is an emotional response to a job situation. As such it cannot be seen, it can only be inferred. Job satisfaction is often determined by how well outcome meet or exceed expectations. Agricultural extension workers are personnel who are responsible for meeting the goals of extension system. However, only little empirical literature exists on the roles and job satisfaction of extension workers in Nigeria. There are sporadic studies on criticism that extension has not being able to perform in bringing the necessary changes in the rural community (Sallam and Akram, 2005). Therefore, it is very critical to know the job satisfaction of extension workers and how this influences their productivity.

1.1 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objective of the study is to identify the determinants of job satisfaction among female agricultural extension agents in Ondo and Ekiti states; the specific objectives were to:

1. ascertain the socio-economic characteristics of the female agricultural extension agents in the study area;
2. identify the roles and responsibilities of the female agricultural extension agents in the study area;
3. determine the level of job satisfaction among the female agricultural extension agents in the study area and
4. determine the attitudes of female agricultural extension workers towards their jobs

1.2 METHODOLOGY

The study was carried out in Ondo and Ekiti states, Nigeria. Ondo state is a state in south-western Nigeria. Ondo state was created on 3 February 1976 from the former western state. Ondo state is situated between latitude 7°10'N and longitude 5.05°E. Ondo state has a total land area of 15,500 square kilometers. It has a population of 3,440,000 according to last population census. It has a population density of 220/km². Ondo state has eighteen local government areas. The major ethnic composition of Ondo state is largely from the Yoruba subgroups of the Akoko, Akure, Ikale, Ilaje, Ondo, and Owo people. The people are mostly subsistence farmers, fishermen and traders. The people are lovers of arts, music and literature. Akure is the capital of the state and also the largest city in the state. Ondo State Agricultural Development project (ODSADEP) is an institution which was created in 1989 when Agricultural Development Project (ADP) was replicated in all the 19 states of the federation as at then (Oseni, 2015). It is structurally divided into two zones, four sub-zones and eighteen Blocks/LGAs (NAERLS, 2012). ODSADEP currently has a total of 100 extension agents with 21 being females and the rest being males

Ekiti state Nigeria was created on 1st of October 1996 alongside five others by the military under the dictatorship of General Sani Abacha. The state was carved out of the territory of the old Ondo state. It is

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situated between 7°40N 5°15°E and 7.667°N 5.250°E. It has an estimated population of 2,737,186. It has sixteen Local Government Areas.

Study population

The study was carried out in Agricultural Development Program (ADP) of Ondo and Ekiti states. The female agricultural extension agents working in the ADP of Ondo state and Ekiti states constituted the population. There are twenty-one (21) female extension workers in ADP Ondo state while there are fourteen (14) in ADP of Ekiti state.

1.3 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Socio-Economic Characteristics of Respondents in the Study Area

Table 1: Age distribution of the respondents

Age Group (Years)	Frequency	Percentage
20-35	8	22.9
36-45	24	68.6
46-55	3	8.6
Total	35	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2015

Table 1 shows the age distributions of female agricultural extension workers in the study area. The study shows that 22.9% of female agricultural extension workers were within 20 – 35 years, while 68.6% are within 36-45 years and 8.6% of female agricultural extension workers were within 46-55 years. The average age of female agricultural extension workers was 42.58 years. The implication of this finding is that the female agricultural extension workers were predominantly in their middle ages, a stage in life when their productivity would be at its peak given an enabling environment.

Marital status

Table 2: Marital status distribution of the respondents

Marital Status	Frequency	Percentage
Married	34	97.1
Missing System	1	2.9
Total	35	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2015

Table 2 revealed that 97.1% of the female agricultural extension workers were married. It could be inferred that almost all of the female agricultural extension workers were married. The implication of this finding is that majority of the female agricultural extension workers are family women.

Religion

Figure 1 shows that majority of the female agricultural extension agents were Christians while 27% were Muslims.

Figure 1: Religion distribution of the respondents

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Source: Field survey, 2015

Educational level

Table 3 shows the highest educational level of the respondents. The entire respondent completed tertiary institution. This implies that all the female agricultural extension workers are highly educated and competent.

Table 3: Highest educational level of the respondents

Educational Level	Frequency	Percentage
Completed Tertiary Institution	35	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2015

Length of service in the institution

Figure 2 shows the years of work experience of the respondents. About 10% of the female agricultural extension workers have served between 1 – 5 years while 80% of the female agricultural extension workers have served between 6 – 10 years while 20% of the female agricultural extension workers have served between 11 – 15 years. The mean of work experience for female agricultural extension workers was 14.25. This implies that the female agricultural extension workers have acquired enough working experience.

Figure 2: Length of service of respondent

Source: Field survey, 2015

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Roles and Responsibility of Female Agricultural Extension Workers

The roles and responsibility of female agricultural extension workers was subjected to a 4 point Likert scale of Frequently (FR), Often (O), Sometimes (SS), and Rarely (R). The total was weighted and the mean was calculated. Any mean between 0.00 – 1.049 was classified Rarely, 1.05 – 2.049 was classified Sometimes, 2.050 – 3.049 was classified Often, while 3.05 – 4.049 was classified Frequently. Table 4a and 4b shows roles and responsibility of female agricultural extension workers. Table 4a shows that the female agricultural extension agents are often being supervised by their supervisors, they often inform clientele about new technology that can boost their production, they also often organize field days for clientele where they are being taught by subject matter specialist and often send clientele problems to the research agencies while they frequently visit the clientele, get in touch with the zonal manager and frequently organize block meeting while table 4b shows that the female agricultural extension agent do employ small plot production techniques in the dissemination of information and practical demonstration to clientele. Table 4b also shows that female extension agents are very effective in their contact with research agencies and farmers.

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Table 4a: Roles and Responsibility of Female Agricultural Extension Workers

Source: Field survey, 2015.

Statement	Rarely		Sometimes		Often		Frequently		Total Score		Decision	
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Mean Score	Final Decision
How often do you visit/have you contact with your clientele in the last one year	1	2.9	4	11.4	16	45.7	14	40	35	100	3.23	F
How often are you in touch with your zonal manager	-	-	1	2.9	26	74.3	8	22.9	35	100	3.2	F
How often are you in touch with subject matter specialist in regards to your clientele's problem	-	-	6	17.1	21	60	7	20	35	100	3.03	O
How often do you organize block meetings	-	-	2	5.7	17	48.6	16	45.7	35	100	3.4	F
How often do you conduct on the spot supervision of the extension agents following the extension agents field visit schedule	-	-	17	48.6	13	37.1	5	14.3	35	100	2.66	O
How often do you inform your clientele about new technologies that could boost their production	4	11.4	21	60	6	17.1	4	11.4	35	100	2.29	O
How often do you organizes field days for your clientele where they are being taught by your subject matter specialists	2	5.7	13	37.1	18	51.4	2	5.7	35	100	2.57	O
How often do you send clientele's problem to the research agencies for solution	-	-	10	28.6	25	71.4	-	-	35	100	2.71	O

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Table 4b: Roles and Responsibility of Female Agricultural Extension Workers

S/N		No		Yes		Totalscore		Decision			
	Statement	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Mean Score	Final Decision		
9	Do you employ the “Small Plot Adoption Technique” (SPATs) in the dissemination of information to your clientele	4	11.4	16	45.7	35	100	0.80	Y		
10	Do you give practical demonstrations to your clientele while on the field	1	2.9	26	74.3	35	100	1.00	Y		
		Fairly Efficient		Efficient		Very Efficient		Totalscore			
		Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%		
11	How efficient are you in your role as a contact man between the agency and the farmer	1	2.9	8	22.9	26	74.3	35	100	2.71	VE

Grand mean=2.19. Source: Field survey, 2015.

Level of Job Satisfaction of the Respondents

The level of job satisfaction of female agricultural extension workers was subjected to a 6 point Likert scale of Agree Very Much (AVM), Agree Moderately (AM), Agree Slightly (AS), Disagree Slightly (DS), Disagree Moderately (DM) and Disagree Very Much (DVM). The total was weighted and the mean was calculated. Any mean between 1.00 – 1.49 was classified disagree very much, 1.50 – 2.49 was classified disagree moderately, 2.50 – 3.49 was classified disagree slightly, 3.5 – 4.49 was classified agree slightly while 4.5 – 5.49 was classified agree moderately and 5.5 -6.00 was classified to agree very much.

Table 5b shows the level of job satisfaction of female agricultural extension workers. The table shows that majority (71.4) % of the female agricultural extension workers are highly satisfied with their level of job satisfaction while 28.6% of the respondents are moderately satisfied

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Table 5a: Level of Job Satisfaction of Female Agricultural Extension Workers

S/N		Disagree Very Much		Disagree Moderately		Disagree Slightly		Agree Slightly		Agree Moderately		Agree Much		Very	Total score	Decision	
	Statement	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Mean Score	Final Decision
1	I feel I am being paid a fair amount for the work I do.	-	-	6	17.1	-	-	2	5.7	22	62.9	5	14.3	35	100	4.57	AM
2	My supervisor is quite competent in doing his/her job.	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	22	62.9	13	37.1	35	100	5.37	AM
3	When I do a good job, I receive the recognition for it that I should receive.	3	8.6	7	20	3	8.6	20	28.6	12	34.3	-	-	35	100	3.60	AS
4	I like the people I work with.	1	2.9	-	-	3	8.6	-	-	14	40.0	17	48.6	35	100	5.29	AM
5	Communications seem good within this organization.	-	-	-	-	1	2.9	2	5.7	2	5.7	29	82.9	35	100	5.74	AVM
6	Those who do well on the job stand a fair chance of being promoted.	1	2.9	5	14.3	-	-	8	22.9	9	25.7	12	34.3	35	100	4.57	AM
7	The benefits we receive are as good as most other organizations offer.	12	34.3	7	20	-	-	2	5.7	19	28.6	4	11.4	35	100	3.09	DS
8	I like doing the things I do at work.	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	12	34.3	23	65.7	35	100	5.66	AVM
9	People get ahead as fast here as they do in other places.	-	-	13	37.1	-	-	14	40.0	7	20.0	1	2.9	35	100	3.51	AS

S/N		Disagree Very Much		Disagree Moderately		Disagree Slightly		Agree Slightly		Agree Moderately		Agree Much		Very	Total score	Decision	
	Statement	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Mean Score	Final Decision
10	The benefit package we have is equitable.	2	5.7	2	5.7	2	5.7	8	22.9	10	28.6	11	31.4	35	100	4.69	AM
11	I enjoy my coworkers.	3	8.6	-	-	-	-	2	5.7	19	54.3	11	31.4	35	100	4.57	AM
12	I feel a sense of pride in doing my job.	-	-	3.0	8.6	-	-	3	8.6	8	22.9	21	60.0	35	100	5.26	AM
13	I feel satisfied with my chances for salary increases.	-	-	3.0	8.6	-	-	2	5.7	19	54.3	11	31.4	35	100	5.00	AM
14	I like my supervisor.	2	5.7	-	-	-	-	7	20.0	14	40.0	10	28.6	35	100	4.85	AM
15	I am satisfied with my chances for promotion.	2	5.7	3	8.6	-	-	5	14.3	21	60	4	11.4	35	100	4.49	AS
16	My job is enjoyable.	2	5.7	-	-	-	-	2	5.7	6	17.1	23	65.7	35	100	5.39	AM

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S/N		Agree Much	Very	Agree Moderately	Agree Slightly	Diasgree Slightly	Disagree Moderately	Disagree Very Much	Total score	Decision							
Statement	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Mean score	Final					
17	There is really too little chance for promotion on my job.	9	25.7	20	57.1	3	8.6	-	-	3	8.6	-	-	35	100	2.09	Decision DM
18	I am not satisfied with the benefits I receive.	11	31.4	9	25.7	3	8.6	4	11.4	4	11.4	4	11.4	35	100	2.80	DS
19	Many of our rules and procedures make doing a good job difficult.	8	22.9	15	42.9	2	5.7	-	-	-	-	-	-	35	100	2.80	DS
20	I sometimes feel my job is meaningless.	21	60.0	9	25.7	1	2.9	2	5.7	-	-	2	5.7	35	100	1.77	DM
21	Raises are too few and far between.	-	-	4	11.4	3	8.6	13	37.1	6	17.1	-	-	35	100	3.81	AS
22	My supervisor is unfair to me.	11	31.4	16	45.7	2	5.7	-	-	5	14.3	1	2.9	35	100	2.29	DM
23	I do not feel that the work I do is appreciated.	13	37.1	16	45.7	2	5.7	-	-	2	5.7	2	5.7	35	100	2.46	DM
24	My efforts to do a good job are seldom blocked by red tape.	19	54.3	11	31.4	1	2.9	2	5.7	2	5.7	-	-	35	100	2.09	DM
25	I find I have to work harder at my job because of the incompetence of people I work with.	19	54.3	11	31.4	1	2.9	2	5.7	2	5.7	-	-	35	100	1.77	DM
26	The goals of this organization are not clear to me.	34	97.1	1	2.9	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	35	100	1.03	DVM
27	I feel unappreciated by the organization when I think about what they pay me.	25	71.4	4	11.4	6	17.1	-	-	-	-	-	-	35	100	2.14	DM

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28	My supervisor shows too little interest in the feelings of subordinates.	14	40.0	15	42.9	-	-	-	-	6	17.1	-	-	35	100	2.11	DM
29	There are few rewards for those who work here.	24	68.6	4	11.4	-	-	1	2.9	4	11.4	2	5.7	35	100	3.71	AS
30	I have too much to do at work.	3	8.6			-	-	3	8.6	8	22.9	21	60.0	35	100	5.37	AM
31	I often feel that I do not know what is going on with the organization.	24	68.6	4	11.4	-	-	1	2.9	4	11.4	2	5.7	35	100	1.94	DM
32	There are benefits we do not have which we should have.	3	8.6	4	11.4	2	5.7	1	2.9	13	37.1	12	34.3	35	100	4.51	AM
33	I have too much paperwork.	2	5.7	4	11.4	-	-	14	40.0	13	37.1	2	5.7	35	100	4.09	AS
34	I don't feel my efforts are rewarded the way they should be.	3	8.6	25	71.4	1	2.7	4	11.4	-	-	2	5.7	35	100	2.40	DM
35	There is too much bickering and fighting at work.	18	51.4	11	31.4	-	-	4	11.4	-	-	2	5.7	35	100	1.94	DM
36	Work assignments are not fully explained.	8	22.9	15	42.9	4	11.4	6	17.1	2	5.7	-	-	35	100	2.40	DM

Grand mean= 3.63. Source: Field survey, 2015

Table 5b: Summary of the Level of Job Satisfaction of Female Agricultural Extension Workers

Satisfaction Level	Frequency	Percentage
Moderate	10	28.6
High	25	71.4
Total	35	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2015

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Table 6: Attitude of Female Agricultural Extension Workers towards their Job

Factors	Mean	Rank	Std. Deviation	Decision
I could be better at my work if I had some/more training or professional development	4.56	1	1.078	SA
I think the organization cares about me as a person as well as an employee	4.38	2	.985	SA
I would recommend this job to others as an employer	4.00	3	.853	SA
I think in general, morale in this job is high.	3.91	4	.893	SA
I think people appreciate the work I do	3.50	5	.896	SA
I think I am paid the right amount for the work I do.	3.47	6	1.051	SA
The clients are easy to work with	3.29	7	1.321	SA
I have asked for training to do my job better	3.15	8	1.282	SA
I received training when I asked for it	3.11	9	1.695	SA
I have the right tools and equipment to do my job	2.65	10	1.276	A
When change is about to happen I am consulted	1.79	11	1.122	D

Grand mean=3.44. *Source:* Field survey, 2015.

Table 6b: Summary of attitude of Female Agricultural Extension Workers towards their Job

Job Attitude	Frequency	Percentage
Low	2	5.7
Moderate	18	51.4
High	15	42.9
Total	35	100.0

Attitude of the respondents were also measured with a 5 point Likert scale of strongly agree (SA), agree (A), neutral (N), disagree (D), and strongly disagree (SD), values of 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 were assigned to positive statements while values of 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1 were assigned to negative statements. The total mean score was calculated, any mean between 1.00 - 1.49 was classified strongly disagreed, from 1.5 – 1.99 was classified disagreed, 2.0 – 2.49 was classified neutral, 2.5 – 2.99 was classified agreed while from 3.0 above was classified strongly agreed. Table 6b shows that 51.4% of the female agricultural extension workers moderately agreed to the attitude towards their job while 42.9% of the female agricultural extension workers highly agreed to the attitude towards their job and the attitude of 5.7% of the respondent towards their job is low.

Determinants of job satisfaction

Table 7: Regression analysis for determinant of job satisfaction

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.336 ^a	.613	-.092	1.216

a. Predictors: (Constant), Promotion, Marital Status, Payment of Allowances, AGE, Official Status, Level of education, Religion

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The results of the multiple regression analysis are presented on Table 7. The result shows that the coefficient of multiple determinations (R^2) was 61.3%. This implies that the variables in the model were able to explain up to 61.3% of the variation in the level of Job Satisfaction among the extension workers of Ondo and Ekiti State. The result also shows that regular payment of allowances, age, level of education, official status and promotion was significantly related to job satisfaction. The above is consistent with apriori expectations since the regular payment of allowances leads to a greater degree of motivation and hence job satisfaction of extension workers. The promotion of the female agricultural extension workers to higher ranks as at when due can go a long way to increase their level of confidence with the organization and hence their level of job satisfaction. Irregular promotion leads to frustration and reduced interest in the job. The level of job satisfaction is also directly related to the level of education of the extension workers, thus the higher the level of education, the higher the level of job satisfaction of the extension workers. Three variables namely; number of years of experience of the extension workers, marital status and religion were found to be negatively related to the level of job satisfaction of female extension workers. The above implies that an increase or rise in any of the variables will lead to a decrease in the level of job satisfaction of the extension workers. Reasons could be due to ageing, fatigue and boredom with the same job over a long period of time

1.4 Conclusion

The study accessed the determinants of job satisfaction among female agricultural extension in Ondo and Ekiti state and concluded that regular payment of allowances, age, level of education, official status and promotion determines to a reasonable extent the level of job satisfaction and showed that majority of female extension workers often perform their role and responsibility.

REFERENCES

- i. Ayangei (2009). *The history of how Agricultural Extension started in Nigeria till present modern extension*. Retrieved from ayangei.wordpress.com/2009/08/13
- ii. Ogunsumi L.O., Abegunde B.O (2011). *Evaluation of Agricultural Extension and Delivery Services in southwest Nigeria: International Journal of Agriscience vol. (14): 185-194, September 2011 ISSN: 2228-6322*
- iii. Sallam, M. & Akram, B. (2005). *Agriculture Extension Situation in Dhamar Province. Dhamar Rural Developmnet Project, Ministry of Agriculture and Irrigation, Yemen*.
- iv. Staudt, Kathleen A(1982). *In Women and Work in Africa "Women Farmers and Inequities in Agricultural Services."*